

RETOOLING SCHEME FOR PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS SCIENCE TEACHERS IN CONDUCTING LABORATORY ACTIVITIES

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ABSTRACT

Teachers must have the theoretical knowledge equipped with abilities to effectively facilitate science teaching. Science education emphasize the importance of rethinking the role and practice of laboratory work in science teaching. This study aimed to assess science teachers' skills in conducting laboratory activities in public secondary schools with the goal of proposing a retooling scheme for science teachers effectively conduct of laboratory activities. The study covered the profile of science teachers, extent of manifestation of science laboratory skills, and the inadequacies of science teachers in conducting science laboratory activities. The study employed the descriptive type of research and used researcher-made questionnaire as main data gathering instrument which is also complemented with interview. Results from the findings revealed that most of the science teachers obtained Masteral units, occupying Teacher I position, Biology major, teaching Science 8, and had attended seminars and trainings related to teaching pedagogical approaches and strategies. They manifest to a moderate extent laboratory skill in Biology, Chemistry, Earth and Space Science and Physics. Also, significant differences were noted in the assessment on the extent of manifestation of laboratory skills when grouped according to profile variables. Moreover, failure to develop is the identified inadequacy of teachers in conducting laboratory activities. The proposed retooling scheme for science teachers envisions to enhance their skills and competencies in conducting laboratory skills towards effective science teaching. The output of this study involved different areas in science with their own objectives, activities and target output.

Keywords: Science, laboratory skills, qualitative descriptive, retooling scheme